

INDICATORS FOR OPTIMIZING CURE TEMPERATURE OF PASTE ADHESIVES

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1 Introduction

The main goal of this research is to optimize the assembly design and the process parameters for robust fast joining of carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) components used in aerospace structures. This research is included in the frame of the European Joint Technology Initiative (JTI) 'Clean sky', focusing on the reduction of environmental impact of air transport.

In this context we are currently investigating the potential of paste adhesive technologies as an alternative to state-of-the-art film-adhesives. An advantage of paste adhesives is that the thickness of the bondline is controlled by the assembly rig, accepting wider tolerances of the bondline thickness than film adhesives. In this case, the bondline thickness is controlled by the adhesive film and accurate bonding partner geometries as well as the use of pressure are required to guarantee good contact in the bondline [1]. Using film adhesives the needed pressure is typically applied by an autoclave, where the complete assembly is heated. Paste adhesives do not require pressure, making it easier to locally heat only the bondline thus reducing the total energy consumption.

Paste adhesives are sensible to exothermal reactions caused by large volumes mixed or by curing processes at high temperature. This can result in degradation of the adhesive system [2], decreasing the mechanical performance in the paste adhesive as well as in the bonded joint. In this study no large volumes are mixed, because typical bondline thicknesses used are about 0.3 mm. The goal of this research is to find a way for fast and robust processing paste adhesives and therefore to develop a methodology to determine the maximum curing temperature.

Bonding joint quality control is today typically done by lap shear tests using CFRP adherents. The results of these tests do not depend only on the quality of the adhesive but also on the quality of the CFRP component. In lap shear tests the samples often fail in the composite adherent, without any damage in

the adhesive system. This study defines a novel method to control the quality of the cured paste adhesives without the need of testing a bonded joint with CFRP adherents.

2 Method

In this contribution, the aim is to study the evolution of different properties which can be used to control the quality of a paste adhesive when high temperatures are used in the curing process. The mainframe of this research is to shorten the curing time of the paste adhesive by increasing the temperature of the process without affecting the mechanical performance of the joint. The paste adhesive system used in this study is LMB 6687-1/LME 10049-3 from Huntsman Advanced Materials. Samples of this paste adhesive are completely cured with a range of different temperatures and times thus obtaining products with different properties to be studied.

Today in industry, mainly low curing temperatures for paste adhesives are requested. The curing process is always done under supplier's recommendations [3]. Effects of an accelerated curing process at higher temperature are typically not considered.

One of the main consequences of too high curing temperatures is degradation in the paste adhesive which leads to an increase of porosity level. When a paste adhesive is mixed, applied to the adherents and cured, a certain quantity of air is entrapped [4]. If the paste adhesive is cured with higher temperatures, the air inside expands more, creating bigger voids thus decreasing the mechanical properties. Typically in industry, the quality of adhesives is tested by shear and peel tests to determine the mechanical performance [5]. Non destructive tests are also used to determine porosity levels, by applying, for example, ultrasonic inspection. Limits of porosity levels are not standardized, but typical values generally accepted are below 2% for primary structures [6]. An example of considerations of porosity levels can be found in literature for levels in

composite panels and limitations about positioning of porosity in the edge to avoid delamination problems, but there are no explicit considerations for bonding systems [7].

Most of the tests considered by state of the art analyze the quality of the paste adhesive after bonding, but do not analyze the paste adhesive alone. The experimental part of this research is based on completely curing the paste adhesive with different temperature cycles, applying a range of temperatures from conservative curing profiles, 80°C for 4 hours recommended by the supplier, until the application of high temperatures, 200°C; causing a clear thermal degradation on the adhesive. Then, the samples are analyzed by different techniques including thermal analysis, optical and mechanical testing thus studying how different properties of the adhesive change with the increment of curing temperature. This study can be used as methodology to set a maximal curing temperature on a paste adhesive by applying the following techniques:

- Thermal analysis techniques are used to observe the evolution of different properties of an epoxy paste adhesive in a temperature range.
 - Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analyzes samples of cured material and the degree of curing is measured, by comparing the energy necessary to cure a fresh sample with the energy necessary to complete the curing chemical reaction of the cured samples. In the case of the paste adhesive used in this study, is recommended by the supplier to achieve a minimum curing degree of 95% for structural applications.
 - Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) is used to observe the evolution of some mechanical properties with the increase of temperatures.
 - Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), heats slowly the sample of paste adhesive until high temperatures, while measuring the weight of the sample. It is used to observe the beginning of thermal degradation of the different components of the paste adhesive and so to set the maximum temperature for the curing process.
- Optical microscopy is used to observe the change of properties e.g. density due to the increment of voids, within the different samples.
- Mechanical tests are also considered, by studying the evolution of mechanical properties, e.g. flexural bending strength and E modulus, when the curing temperature is changed.

In this research, the relation between curing temperature and mechanical performance is studied and the optimal curing temperature for fast curing of paste adhesives is determined. Studied properties are compared with simple lap shear bonded joints with CFRP adherents, which represent the state of the art. The results of this study show other approaches to assess the quality of a cured paste adhesive system that are independent from the adherents.

3. Election and preparation of samples

The reference curing profile, recommended by the provider is 80°C for 4 hours. The rest of the curing profiles used in this study are defined using the kinetics model of the curing reaction.

The modeling of the chemical reaction follows Arrhenius relation [8] based on the nth order kinetics [9], shown in equation 1:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

This model has three degrees of freedom: the curing degree α , temperature T and time t and three parameters which characterize the reaction: k_0 , E and n , and which differ in each chemical product. With these values it is possible to predict which will be the curing degree for a certain temperature applied during a certain time. The equation can be rewritten depending on the curing degree as follows:

$$\alpha = 1 - \left[1 - (1 - n) z t \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right)\right]^{\frac{1}{1-n}} \quad (2)$$

A single dynamic heating measurement is carried out in the DSC with a non-cured sample of the paste adhesive and, the kinetics model is established applying multiple regression. In order to minimize the error in the measurement, 8 measurements are carried out and the average values are used to set the relation between temperature, time and curing degree, shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Model of the curing reaction.

Curing temperatures used in this study go from 80 to 200 °C and curing times are given by the model. It must be considered that samples will have a certain gelling stage not considered in the theoretical model, so the real curing degree will be slightly higher. For this reason a curing degree of 90% has been considered minimum to select curing times, which are summarized in table 1.

Sample	Temperature [°C]	Time [min]	Model curing degree [%]
1	80	240	93.2
2	100	60	91.3
3	120	60	95.6
4	140	45	97.1
5	160	30	97.8
6	180	15	97.8
7	200	10	98.2

Table 1: Summary of curing conditions of samples.

The paste adhesive used in all the experiments is mixed thoroughly with a centrifuge mixer model SpeedMixer DAC 150.1 FV three times for 1 minute at 1500 rpm. Then, the paste adhesive is applied and then kept at room temperature (21°C) for a gelling stage of two hours and then heated in a heat press model ‘Fontijne Holland TP 400’ following the different curing processes.

For the single lap shear test, used commonly as state of the art for qualification of bonded joints, an out of autoclave CFRP system from ACG is used, MTM-44-1. Samples are prepared following recommendations from the supplier. Surfaces of the produced plates are treated with a manual sanding process, using a size of P100. Then the plates are thoroughly cleaned firstly with acetone, then with

tap water and finally with de-ionized water. Then, CFRP plates are dried in a forced convection oven for 2 hours at 65°C. Once the surface treatment is complete, bonding process is carried out by applying the same procedure than for the rest of experiments, leaving for two hours the bonded samples at room temperature and then curing under the different temperatures in the heat press.

4. Results

4.1. Thermal analysis

DSC analysis is carried out to measure the curing degree of the samples. A non cured sample is completely cured and the total amount of energy released in the reaction, in this case 320.04 J/g, is calculated as average of 8 measurements. Then, samples heated under the different curing profiles are analyzed in the DSC completing the reaction and measuring the energy released. Curing degrees of different samples are summarized in table 2.

Sample	Released energy [J/g]	Curing degree [%]
1	10.5	96.7
2	7.6	97.6
3	7.6	97.6
4	8.4	97.4
5	11.4	96.4
6	12.5	96.1
7	3.1	99.0

Table 2: Curing degree of samples measured by DSC.

All the samples are cured more than 95%, the curing process is considered complete.

A 3 point bending test is carried out in the DMA for the different samples measuring the storage modulus in a range of temperatures as well as T_g, as seen in table 3.

Sample	Storage mod. at 20°C [Pa]	T _g [°C]
1	4.43E+08	111.8
2	3.29E+08	112.8
3	2.85E+08	116.5
4	1.97E+08	120.2
5	1.05E+08	122.0
6	6.00E+07	130.7
7	1.05E+08	120.4

Table 3: Storage modulus at 20 °C and T_g values.

It can be observed that the storage modulus at 20 °C, decreases within the samples cured at higher

temperature. Tg increases slightly in samples cured at higher temperature.

TGA analysis is also considered. The hardener and epoxy are heated until 1000°C by separate and also mixed, in order to observe loss of mass. Results set the onset of the hardener at 148.6°C and in the resin at 214.9°C but loss of mass can be observed in the hardener at about 120°C, meaning that samples heated with this temperature or more, will have a higher percentage of voids. TGA of the mixed sample is also considered having similar results.

4.2. Optical study

The microscope model Leica DM RXA is used to observe voids inside of the paste adhesive and to measure porosity. This measurement is repeated 10 times in the area inside the frame that can be observed in the pictures, covering different areas on the samples to have a more homogeneous measurement. Examples of each sample are shown in figures 2 to 8.

Fig. 2. Sample cured at 80 °C.

Fig. 3. Sample cured at 100 °C

Fig. 4. Sample cured at 120 °C.

Fig. 5. Sample cured at 140 °C

Fig. 6. Sample cured at 160 °C

Fig. 7. Sample cured at 180 °C

Fig. 8. Sample cured at 200 °C

Average diameter values of the voids are also calculated by measuring values in ten different voids for each sample. Results are summarized in table 4.

Sample	Average bubble's diameter [μm]	Porosity [%]
1	48.8 \pm 22.4	1.6 \pm 0.5
2	61.7 \pm 31.6	1.4 \pm 0.5
3	103.6 \pm 28.8	2.1 \pm 0.8
4	229.0 \pm 75.7	21.4 \pm 6.2
5	262.9 \pm 132.0	33.5 \pm 11.6
6	334.5 \pm 236.0	60.5 \pm 17.0
7	265.9 \pm 181.8	75.1 \pm 12.2

Table 4: Summary of optical measurements.

As it can be observed from pictures and results, the porosity levels as well as the size of the voids increase when the curing temperature is increased.

4.3. Mechanical testing

A 3 point bending test is carried out in a standard tensile test machine, following the ISO 178 for

determination of flexural properties in plastics. Percentile density is also calculated, relating weight to pure epoxy density given by the provider (1.1 Kg/dm³). Results are summarized in table 5.

Sample	E modulus [MPa]	Bending stress [MPa]	Density [%]
1	1098.5 \pm 122.3	41.4 \pm 4.0	97.6
2	1190.4 \pm 106.3	44.2 \pm 1.9	98.7
3	1062.3 \pm 74.8	41.2 \pm 2.3	95.1
4	649.7 \pm 120.0	24.5 \pm 5.9	80.7
5	474.0 \pm 168.0	15.4 \pm 5.8	61.2
6	194.5 \pm 107.0	5.6 \pm 2.9	41.0
7	115.0 \pm 23.3	2.9 \pm 0.9	25.1

Table 5: Summary of results in 3 point bending test.

The results of 3 point bending test show that the mechanical properties and the density level decrease when a higher temperature is used in the curing process.

Finally, a Single lap shear (SLS) test is carried out under EN 2243-1 for structural adhesives, for CFRP bonded samples applying the different curing profiles. This test is common state of the art in aerospace industry. Five samples are tested for each curing profile. Results and fracture modes are characterized and summarized in figure 9 and table 6.

Fig. 9. SLS test for CFRP bonded samples.

Sample	Shear stress [MPa]	Fracture mode
1	24.44 \pm 2.90	Adherent
2	22.12 \pm 1.84	Adherent
3	16.28 \pm 1.22	Cohesive
4	15.50 \pm 1.58	Cohesive
5	6.04 \pm 1.30	Adhesive
6	6.06 \pm 0.52	Adhesive
7	6.58 \pm 1.40	Adhesive

Table 6: Results of simple lap shear test.

Results show a decrease of shear stress when the curing temperature is increased and adhesive failure in samples that are highly degraded. Typically in aerospace joints, values about 30MPa are expected. In this study lower values were obtained due to the quality of the adherent, having an optimal performance of the adhesive until the fracture of the adherent on samples cured at lower temperature.

5. Conclusions

Optimal temperature for curing paste adhesive is 100°C for one hour for its use in primary structures, saving 75% of the time comparing with recommended curing conditions and keeping the mechanical properties. Curing with temperatures equal or higher than 120°C will produce thermal degradation of the paste adhesive through the evaporation of some particles which will create new voids, combined with the growing of the voids already trapped during the mixing process. This will cause a decrease on the mechanical properties of the paste adhesive. Results are confirmed by most of the measured properties and also by the state of the art, single lap shear test, showing adherent fracture for samples cured between 80°C and 100°C and a weaker cohesive failure in samples cured with higher temperature, showing also a decrease of mechanical performance due to the porosity increment.

All the analyzed properties show a similar tendency, but most of them have drawbacks that do not recommend its use to assess quality of paste adhesives. DMA measurements do not show a clear point where degradation is started do not differ between curing at 100°C, where the paste adhesive has good quality, and curing at 120°C, when the paste adhesive is degraded. TGA analysis cannot explain the entire decrease of performance because the evaporation of particles can only explain formation of new voids and not the expansion of voids trapped in the mixing process. Mechanical and density measurements require big samples to be tested, not always possible to acquire from real applications, where the access to the bondline can be limited, and also do not differ between curing at 100°C and 120°C.

Finally, optical analysis is found to be the most restrictive and clear indicator to assess the bonding quality, having the possibility to analyze the quality of the bonding system with a small sample. This method restricts the use of curing at 120°C for primary structures, having a porosity value higher

than 2%, and bubbles which are found to clearly increase in size compared with samples cured with lower temperatures.

Analysis of porosity and voids is an accurate method to assess the quality of a cured paste adhesive, by a simple optical study with the microscope. This technique can be used as complement for single lap shear tests, being especially useful because does not depend on the quality of any other material, like the adherent in destructive techniques. In this study it is shown that void diameter and porosity levels of the paste adhesive can be precisely measured and represent the quality of the paste adhesive under study.

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